

Geotabs Questionnaire

Please select your Gender

- Female
- Male

1. How did you arrive to work today?

- By Car
- By Public transportation (Taxi, Bus, Train, etc.)
- By Bike
- By Foot

2. How long have you been in the office before filling in this questionnaire?

Please select Please select

3. What are you wearing at this moment (please mark everything)?

- Pants
- Skirt
- Singlet
- Sneakers
- Shorts
- Dress
- Underwear
- Boots
- T-shirt
- Jacket
- Socks
- Shoes
- Shirt
- Sweater
- Stockings
- Mokasen

4. please indicate your current location on the floorplan

+2

+3

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10
- 11
- 12
- 13
- 14

5. How do you feel at this moment?

6. How do you perceive this...?

7. Would you like it to be?

8. How do your local body parts feel?

a.1. your hands

a.2. How do you perceive this...?

b.1, your arms

b.2. How do you perceive this...?

c.1 your feet

c.2. How do you perceive this...?

d.1 your head

d.2. How do you perceive this...?

e.1 your trunk

e.2. How do you perceive this...?

9. what do you think the temperature is at this moment?

Please select

10. If you had the possibility to change the temperature, would you do so?

- Yes
- No

If yes, how important is it for you to change the thermal environment?

11. Do you feel any air movement around ...?

a.1. your hands

a.2. How do you perceive this...?

b.1, your arms

b.2. How do you perceive this...?

b.1, your arms

b.2. How do you perceive this...?

c.1 your feet

c.2. How do you perceive this...?

d.1 your head

d.2. How do you perceive this...?

e.1 your trunk

e.2. How do you perceive this...?

12. How comfortable is the overall air movement for you?

13. would you prefer?

- More air movement
- No Change
- Less air movement

14. are any windows or doors near you open, at this moment?

- Yes
- No

15. Do you have control over window or door opening?

- Yes
- No

16. How do you assess the air quality in your office at the moment?

17. How do you assess the indoor air at the moment?

18. How do you assess the Noise level in your office at the moment?

19. Which of the following controls do you have over the lighting in your office?

- Light Switch
- Light Dimmer
- Window blinds or shades
- Desk light
- None of the above

20. How do you assess the color of the lighting in your office at the moment?

21. How do you assess the brightness of the lighting in your office at the moment?

22. At this moment, are you experiencing?

a. A headache?

b. Nose irritation (stuffy or running)?

c. Throat irritation?

d. Fatigue?

e. Dry Eyes?

f. Concentration?

g. Alertness?

h. Right now, completion of tasks requires?

i. Right now, I am able to work?

This information will only be used for research by the project partners of the hybridGEOTABS project (H2020 project nr. 723649) and will not be distributed to outsiders. For an inquiry about your data, you may contact hybridgeotabs@ugent.be

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